

Extraction and Photometric Studies of Cu(II) with Tetramethylthiuram Disulphide

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The solvent extraction and photometric studies of Cu(II) with tetramethylthiuram disulphide are reported. The yellowish coloured complex is extractable in chloroform at pH 3.5. It has $\lambda_{\max}$ at 435 nm and obeys Beer's law in the concentration range of 0.31 to 4.8 μg of copper per ml of the solution. Maximum extraction takes place in the pH range 3.5 to 4.5. The complex is stable for more than 24 hr. The effect of various interfering ions has also been studied.

In the present work, solvent extraction properties of Cu(II) with tetramethylthiuram disulphide (abbreviated as TMTD) have been studied. The reagent is also known as bis(dimethyl thiocarbamoyl) disulphide. It contains two thiocarbamoyl groups and has the structure

Babaeva and Derbisher have reported the reaction of TMTD with some complex compounds of platinum and palladium¹. Its reaction with copper is known and this reaction has been used for the determination of TMTD² and also for the colorimetric determination of mercury³ and silver⁴. The use of this reagent for the colorimetric determination of copper^{5,6} and tellurium⁷ has been reported. References about its compounds with cobalt⁸ and salts of heavy metals⁹ are found in literature. The present work deals with the extractability of copper with TMTD under different experimental conditions and the use of the colour of the chloroform extract for the photometric determination of traces of copper. The method is more modified and improved as compared to one suggested earlier^{5,6}. The spectra, values of molar absorptivity and sensitivity, effect of pH on extraction, range of adherence to Beer's law, effect of solvents, effect of reagent concentration and precision of determination are reported for the first time in this paper. Co^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Na^+ , K^+ , Br^- , I^- , CrO_4^{2-} and citrate do not interfere in the determination but Fe^{3+} and Al^{3+} do. This is contrary to what has been reported earlier. The method suggested here is more precise and total time required for complete operation is 20 minutes.

Experimental

Apparatus: A pH-meter (Electronics Corporation of India) with glass-calomel electrode system was

used for the adjustment of pH. A Bausch and Lomb spectronic 20 colorimeter, with 1 cm glass cells was used for absorbance measurements.

Reagents: A solution of copper sulphate (0.01M) was prepared by dissolving a known weight of AnalaR grade copper sulphate in distilled water. The solution required in the experiment (0.001M) was prepared by suitable dilution of the above solution. Freshly prepared solutions were always used in the experiments.

TMTD was prepared by the oxidation of corresponding dithiocarbamic acid with iodine¹⁰. It was crystallised from alcohol. The melting point and composition values were in agreement with the reported values. This purified sample was used in the experiments.

General Procedure: An aliquot of solution containing 55 μg of copper was taken and its pH was adjusted to 3.5 with dil. HCl in a total volume of 50 ml. The solution was heated to boiling for 2-3 min and to it was then added 3.0 ml freshly prepared alcoholic TMTD solution of $1.33 \times 10^{-2}M$ strength. The solution was boiled further for 2 min and cooled. This solution was shaken with two 10 ml portions of chloroform for 2 min each. The combined chloroform extract was taken in a 20 ml volumetric flask. The absorbance of the yellow coloured solution was then measured at 435 nm against chloroform blank. The amount of copper present was determined from a calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra: The spectra of TMTD alone (A) and Cu(II)-TMTD complex (B) are given in Figure 1. The complex shows maximum absorbance at 435 nm while absorbance of the reagent shows a continuous decrease. The difference in absorbance is maximum at 435 nm. All absorbance measurements were, therefore, made at this wavelength. The molar absorptivity of the complex is calculated.

When copper concentration is 63 μg and cell width is 1 cm, absorbance is 0.710 at 435 nm. The molar absorptivity then comes to be 1.43×10^4 .

Fig. 1. Spectra of Reagent (A) and Complex (B).

Extraction as a function of pH: The extraction of copper was carried out at different pH values. Percentage extraction was calculated with the help of a calibration curve and results obtained are given in Table 1. Extraction is quantitative in the pH range 3.5 to 4.5. Below and beyond this pH, there is decrease in extraction. The optimum pH range for quantitative extraction is from 3.5 to 4.5.

TABLE I. EFFECT OF pH ON EXTRACTION

pH	Extraction %	Distribution Ratio, D
2.0	41.25	1.75
2.5	61.25	3.95
3.0	72.50	6.59
3.5	99.00	247.50
4.0	99.00	247.50
4.5	99.00	247.50
5.0	80.00	10.00
6.0	73.75	7.02

Beer's law: The range of concentration that adheres to Beer's law was found by taking different amounts of copper and extracting at pH 3.5. The Cu(II)-TMTD system conforms to Beer's law in the concentration range of 0.31 to 4.8 μg of copper per ml of the solution.

Stability of colour at room temperature: The absorbance of the yellow coloured solution was measured at different time intervals. It was found to remain constant for more than 24 hr.

Effect of solvents: In addition to chloroform, various other solvents such as benzene, carbon tetrachloride, hexan-1-ol, 2-methyl propan-1-ol, iso-amyl alcohol, 1-pentanol, 1-butanol were tried for extraction. It was found that most suitable solvent for quantitative extraction of copper was either benzene or chloroform.

Effect of reagent concentration: The extraction of copper was carried out with varying concentration

and varying volume of the reagent. The concentration of copper was kept constant (63 μg). The extraction was done by adding varying volume (1 to 5 ml) of $1.33 \times 10^{-2} M$ TMTD solution and also by adding 3 ml of varying concentration (1.0×10^{-2} , 1.33×10^{-2} , 1.5×10^{-2} , 1.67×10^{-2} and $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$) of TMTD solution. It was found that extraction is quantitative with 3 ml of $1.33 \times 10^{-2} M$ of the reagent.

Effect of salting out agents: With other factors being kept constant, 3 to 10 ml of 1 to 3M solutions of the chlorides and nitrates of alkali metals and alkaline earths were tested as salting out agents. However, none of them were capable to enhance extraction.

Effect of diverse ions: The effect of the presence of various anions and cations on the extraction of 63 μg of copper was studied. Standard solutions of the ions were prepared. A known and varying volume of the solution was added to the extracting system keeping final dilution same. The tolerance limit for each ion was calculated at that concentration where a change of $\pm 2\%$ in the determination of copper was noted. Table 2 shows the tolerance limit of various ions.

TABLE 2. EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS

Ion	Added as	Tolerance limit (mg)
Co ²⁺	CoSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	12.2
Mg ²⁺	MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	7.5
Zn ²⁺	ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	16.5
Cd ²⁺	CdSO ₄ ·8/3H ₂ O	15.0
Na ⁺	NaCl	20.0
K ⁺	KCl	70.0
Br ⁻	KBr	20.0
I ⁻	KI	200.0
CrO ₄ ²⁻	K ₂ CrO ₄	12.8
Citrate	Potassium citrate	140.0

It was found that Fe³⁺, Mn²⁺, Ni²⁺, Pb²⁺, Ba²⁺, Al³⁺, NO₃⁻, EDTA, SCN⁻ and oxalate interfere at all concentrations.

The precision and accuracy of the method was tested by analysing solutions containing known amounts of copper. The relative mean deviation was $\pm 0.12\%$. The sensitivity (Sandell's) of measurement was found to be 0.0044 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$. The method is simple, rapid, and applicable to trace quantities of copper.

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References

1. A. V. BABAEVA and G. V. DERBISHER, *Zh Neorg. Khim.*, 1962, 7, 2689.
2. S. AKERSTORM and P. F. BJORN LINDAHL, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1962, 1206.

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3. A. L. GERSHUNS, E. I. VAIL, A. P. MIRANAYA, I. A. RASTREPINA and L. V. SIGALOVA, 1961, 27, 1465, CA. vol 56, 1962, 10903b.
4. A. I. GERSHUNS and L. Z. KALMYKOV, *Zavodskaya Lab.*, 1960, 26, 152. CA. vol 154, 1960, 11848c.
5. S. M. GUSEIN-ZADE, *Doklady. Akad. Nauk. Azerbaidzhan. S.S.R.*, 1953, 9, 321. *Referat. Zhur. Khim.*, 11218, 1954. *Chem. Abs.* 1955, 49, 1470d.
6. G. MEXZARAUPS, A. KAULA, M. DZINTARNIEKS, J. BANBOVKIS and A. IEVINS, *Latv. PSR Zinet Akad. Vestis. Kim. Ser.*, 1966, 441.
7. V. TUTKUVINE and RAMANAUSKAS, *Zh. Analit. Khim.*, 1966, 21, 564.
8. H. CONTRERAS and H. CORTES, *Inorg. Nuclear Chem. Letters*, 1970, 6, 225.
9. SARJU PRASAD and P. B. SHARMA, *J. Proc. Inst. Chemists (India)*, 1958, 30, 259.
10. G. D. THORN and R. A. LUDWIG, "The Dithiocarbamates and Related Compounds". Elsevier Publishing Company, New York, 1962 p. 61.